

Development of Feature Binding in Children: A Critical Review

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The integrated representation of different properties of a stimulus is feature binding. The process of binding provides mental representations, which are required for all higher cognitive processes. Several researchers have identified various factors affecting feature binding. In recent years, researchers have also studied the development of the ability for binding features. This review surveys the theories and experiments regarding the developmental trajectory of feature binding. Models such as those conceptualizing fixed number of slots in working memory, those emphasizing precision due to the processing demand, and those stressing the dynamic nature of cognition over the period of development, are considered. Studies of infants and children are critically analysed, with the conclusion that the classic constructivist approaches, such as those of Piaget and Bruner, must be invoked to understand the developmental stages in forming mental representations through feature binding.

Keywords: Feature binding, development, infants, children

At any time, there are many stimuli in the environment which compete for our attention, each with several different features. Feature binding is the process whereby different characteristics, such as size, shape, colour, orientation, and location, coded in different areas in the brain (Milner & Goodale, 1995) are integrated as a mental representation to create an object in the mind. Binding is essential for veridical perception of the world. It individuates objects in a pattern, and indeed, helps form the pattern in the first place, by separating the figure(s) from the ground.

Feature binding is essential for myriad cognitive functions. The parallel processing of different objects and/or their features (Von der Malsburg, 1981), combining new sounds and words in the production of language (Fodor & Pylyshyn, 1988), the search for the neural correlates of consciousness (Crick & Koch, 1990), the formation and development of our self-system as perceived (Metzinger, 1995), establishment of self-related, proprioceptive time frames regarding the past and future (Poppel, 1997), the use of memory and reasoning to analyse and solve real world problems (Halford et al., 2007), all require integrated mental representations which result from the process of feature binding. Feature binding deficits are cognitive markers of Alzheimer's disease (Koppara et al.,

2015; Parra et al., 2010). Visual feature binding deficits also portend non-verbal learning difficulties in children (Garcia et al., 2015) whereas visual-phonological binding deficits are implicated in dyslexia among children (Albano et al., 2016).

The study of feature binding began in earnest only in the 1980s with the seminal work of Treisman and Gelade (1980). Research has identified several important factors in binding visual features, such as attention as a resource, complexity of the stimuli, relevance of features, location as a special feature, and so on. Attention is often proposed to be the cognitive mechanism crucial for feature binding. The feature integration theory, first espoused by Treisman and Gelade (1980) and later enunciated by Treisman and Sato (1990) proposed that attention, focused on different locations, led to the instantaneous binding of features present in that location. Researchers who studied feature binding in visual working memory (Jaswal, 2013; Logie et al., 2011; Treisman & Zhang, 2006) emphasized the selective, top-down nature of attention in feature binding, whereby only relevant features are bound and the irrelevant ones are discarded from the bound representations. This is equally true of irrelevant objects also, the target objects acquiring clarity with focussed attention in comparison to the other objects, whereas the distracters recede into the background. *Inter alia*, this also makes location a special feature as attention is the glue that binds together features at particular locations (Jaswal, 2013; Treisman & Gelade, 1980).

Nevertheless, relatively few researchers have focused on the developmental aspect of feature binding, i.e., how this capacity is acquired, how it changes over time, or how it is manifested in the various stages of development. The few research studies on development of feature binding in the context of working memory can be understood as two rather distinct streams. The first set of research focuses on infancy (reviewed by Reznick, 2009). The other set of studies address middle childhood and adults (reviewed by Cowan, 2016).

Infants obviously lack the behavioural repertoire of adults and hence studies of infants are limited to those that use looking and/or

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reaching as the responses in their paradigms. Across these tasks, results have converged to a general pattern (Reznick, 2009; Rose et al., 2004). As infants grow and develop, mental representations are formed sooner in memory, and can be maintained for longer periods. With increasing age, Infants can also use these representations more often and clearly during search and recognition tasks. They also start representing more complex information as they grow. Researchers propose that developing neural circuits which support visual working memory are primarily responsible for these changes (e.g., the prefrontal cortex, Diamond, 1990; Ross-Sheehy et al., 2003; or parietal regions, Oakes et al., 2009), resulting in a boost to cognitive processes such as inhibition (Diamond, 1990), or object individuation (Oakes et al., 2009). As an example, consider the research on 144 children by Ross-Sheehy et al. (2003) who examined the binding of object defining colour and location in infants who were 6.5 to 12.5 months old. In a previous study, they had established that at the tender age of 6.5 months, infants could separately represent both colour and location as single features in visual short-term memory. In this study, they found that infants of this age of 6.5 months old infants could not remember combinations of colour and location even across a time period of 300 ms. However, infants who were 7.5 months old could remember bindings of colour and location as effectively as infants who were 12.5 months old. This rapid development of the binding function in visual short term memory between 6.5 and 7.5 months is presumably associated with a marked increase in visual short-term memory storage capacity. The latter is further correlated with substantial neuroanatomical changes in the parietal cortex. So, they concluded that the ability to integrate separate features and store a pattern of individuated objects may both be contingent on focussed attention, a process often anatomically attributed to the posterior parietal cortex.

Studies of visual working memory during early to middle childhood typically use tasks similar to the ones used in research with adults, such as the change detection task (e.g., Luck & Vogel, 1997). In this task, participants are shown a small number of simple objects in the initial display (called the memory array). Thereafter, following a short delay, another set of objects is presented as the test array, in which the items either match the initially shown memory array or one or more have changed. Participants have to respond whether the memory and test arrays are 'same' or 'different'. Most of these developmental studies have examined memory for single features such as colours (e.g., Cowan et al., 2002; Isbell et al., 2015) or shapes (e.g., Simmering et al., 2015) and have reported that with increasing age, there is a gradual enhancement of performance as well (reviewed by Simmering & Perone, 2013).

Using a different paradigm, Lorscheid and Reimer (2010) compared memory for individual features (objects or locations) with the memory for combined features (objects & locations) among students who were either 9, 12, or 21 years old, using a simple yes or no recognition task. They found that although differences due to age existed in both tasks, they were greater in the task that required memory for conjunctions of object and locations. Using hierarchical multiple regression analyses, they statistically removed the performance in object and location conditions and their interactive effect as predictors. They found that age remained a significant predictor of memory performance in the combination condition. Thus, their results show evidence for differences in the memory for binding of features with increasing age. Brockmole and Logie (2013) have provided a more comprehensive analysis of age-related

changes in visual working memory. They assessed visual working memory abilities of 55,753 individuals between the ages of 8 and 75 through an online study. Results showed that visual working memory changes throughout the life span, peaking at age 20. Thereafter, there is a steady decline which becomes quite apparent over time. By age 55, adults have worse immediate visual memory than 8 - 9 year old children. This pattern of development is likely due to changes in visual working memory capacity and difficulties in visual feature binding process among children and older adults.

All such results are usually considered as proof for a developmental increase in visual working memory capacity. Simply speaking, capacity refers to the number of stimuli that can be held in the memory store at any given instant. This interpretation is consonant with the conceptualization of visual working memory as having a few 'slots', which can hold only a limited and fixed number of separate representations (e.g., Cowan, 2001; Luck & Vogel, 1997). Most theorists of visual working memory development adhere to this idea. For example, Cowan proposed that the number of 'chunks' held in the focus of attention increase over development (e.g., Cowan et al., 2002). Through different manipulations in a series of studies, Cowan and his colleagues have shown that other changes in other cognitive processes, such as the use of specific strategies or increases in knowledge in general, do not account for the better performance with increasing age among children (see review by Cowan, 2016). Cowan (2013) proposed that such improvements actually manifest increases in capacity itself, although he pointed out that the fundamental source(s) of capacity increases were not clear.

Those against the idea that working memory capacity is reflected in a fixed number of slots have proposed another experimental task which assesses the precision of visual working memory representations (Bays & Husain, 2008; Fougine, Cormiea, & Alvarez, 2013). Three different studies have used this task to measure developmental changes in precision. Burnett-Heyes et al. (2012) found that 7 to 13 year old children showed a similar pattern to adults, in that they also demonstrated a load-precision trade off. They also found better precision in older children. Two years later, the same children were tested in a longitudinal study (Burnett-Heyes et al., 2016) and it was found that the precision of the performance of children had improved with age. Probabilistic modelling of responses indicated that the improvements in precision performance with age were associated with reduction in noise (errors) in memory representations. In contrast, however, a study by Sarigiannidis et al. (2016) comparing 79 year old and 1012 year old groups of children found that it was not precision that increased with age, but that there was a decrease in incorrect-target responses (i.e., recalling a feature from an un-cued item), which resulted in overall performance increments. Together, these results indicate improvements in children's performance with development, but conflicting results from further analyses do not yield clarity as to whether the improvements are due to increased precision, or better inhibition of irrelevant representations and hence improved selection from memory, or both.

Despite the slots vs. resources debate, behavioural evidence clearly suggests that visual working memory improves in several different aspects from infancy, through middle childhood, to adulthood. During infancy, as the brain matures, the time during which a memory representation is built steadily reduces. These representations are maintained and used more readily and robustly

with development. The mental representations also grow in complexity with age. Maturational changes in the brain probably underlie all these outcomes (Knickmeyer et al., 2008). During childhood, as the aforementioned studies show, both capacity and precision of memory likely increase, but unfortunately research has been designed to address only either one of these characteristics. To bridge these diverse tasks and age groups, and to provide a more comprehensive theory, Simmering (2016) proposed the cognitive dynamics theory. This idea especially emphasizes continuity in development and the interdependence of processing involved in a plethora of tasks. Earlier, Johnson and Simmering (2015) had proposed the architecture of a model to simulate working memory tasks. Their model included two excitatory layers, one perceptual and the other for working memory, and a shared inhibitory layer. There was continuous interaction among these three layers throughout the task. Excitation started and projected not only from the perceptual layer to the inhibitory and working memory layers, but also from the working memory to the inhibitory layer, besides the inhibitory layer projecting back into both the excitatory layers. In this stormy sea of excitation vs. inhibition, stimuli incessantly compete for representation, which results in the limited capacity of working memory as demonstrated by Franconeri et al. (2013). This store is not considered as having a strict limit, unlike the slot-like conceptualizations. If the task is difficult and requires greater cognitive resources, capacity may be limited to one. On the other hand, if the task is easy and less demanding, capacity may expand up to three or four. So, the capacity limit changes according to task demands (Johnson et al., 2014).

The transactions among separate layers also provide an implicit mechanism for comparative analyses of memory representations and new input. Familiar or old items require reduced perceptual processing. In contrast, new items, possessing features or their values not previously held in working memory, produce a novelty signal with strong activation in the perceptual layer. This comparative mechanism accounts for habituation (Perone & Spencer, 2013) and preference for novelty or new stimuli in "looking" paradigms often used with children (for example, Perone & Spencer, 2014). This same mechanism may explain performance in the change detection task, where the participant has to decide whether the probe is "same" or "different" from the initially shown array of items in the memory display (Simmering, 2016). The comparative mechanism also underlies performance in single-item colour discrimination tasks (Simmering & Patterson, 2012).

Further, a single type of developmental change, strengthening connectivity within and between layers in the model, can explain improvements that occur with increasing age, in habituation (Perone & Spencer, 2013), visual paired comparison (Perone et al., 2011; Perone & Spencer, 2013, 2014), colour discrimination (Simmering & Patterson, 2012), change detection (Simmering, 2016; Simmering et al., 2015), and tasks of spatial memory (Simmering, Schutte, & Spencer, 2008). This change in connectivity implies that the balance of excitation and inhibition existing in the model at any given time does not last forever. The stability is prone to change with time and development, and is therefore termed "real-time" stability (Simmering & Wood, 2017).

Early forms of behaviour are unpredictable, unreliable, and also lack coordination. Collectively, one may say that they are unstable. Through repetition, which allows better coordination, behaviour becomes reliable and predictable. Transfer is possible and actions

are applied broadly, such as attempts to grasp objects of different shapes and sizes, to wear and walk in the shoes of a parent. Sequences of actions are also more resistant to disruption or disturbance, such as keep standing or walking on uneven surfaces, or not losing one's grasp of an object merely because someone else holds the arm. Simmering (2016) extended the idea of "real time stability" visual working memory, conceptualizing the notion as the basis for the collective improvement in the formation, maintenance, and use of mental representations in service of current behavioural goals.

Simmering and Wood (2017) specifically tested the real-time stability hypothesis in the context of feature binding in visual working memory. Theirs was the first study which tested children younger than 7 years using the change detection task, and specifically compared single feature changes and multi-feature changes in these young children. They hypothesized that the unstable, uncoordinated cognitive architecture of children leads to rather poor localization of features, which particularly hampers the process of feature binding in visual working memory. However, their experiments showed some surprising results. As mentioned earlier, they probed visual working memory using a change detection task that compared changes in single features to swaps in colour-shape binding. In the first experiment, 3 to 4 year-old children showed impairments specific to binding swaps, as was predicted on the basis of lower real time stability in this early stage of development. But, children who were 5 to 6 years old showed better performance in the detection of bindings than single features, and 7 to 8 year old children and adults showed no difference across the different types of change.

Notably, Simmering and Wood (2017) did not further explore the better performance of 5 to 6 year old children in detecting binding as compared to single feature changes, proposing three possible explanations in their discussion for this anomalous result. First, it could be a specious finding resulting from the huge variability in performance that children often manifest in any task. Second, despite random assignment, due to the separate-groups design of the experiments, it could happen that children in the contrasting age groups differed systematically in their cognitive abilities in the single feature and binding conditions. Lastly, they contended that binding-swaps may have been easier to detect than new-feature changes as the binding condition necessarily has two items which swap, and thus two change signals in every trial. In contrast, the new feature condition has only one change signal.

Nevertheless, none of these explanations are satisfactory as they are equally applicable to all conditions and age groups. The question remains as to why should only children between 5-6 years of age show an improvement in memory for binding as compared to memory for single features? Perhaps we should consider the classic constructivist theories regarding stages of cognitive development for understanding this experimental result.

Piaget (1951), the pioneer of the constructivist approach, indicated that the preoperational stage lasts from about two to about seven years old. In this stage, the child possesses relatively stable mental representations, which in turn enable pretend play and the use of symbols. Also, there is a clear understanding of time, of what has gone past, and what is in the future. But the thinking of the child is unidimensional. This makes the child egocentric during this stage, that is, she sees things from only one point of view, usually from her own. Children center on one aspect of any problem or

communication at a time. This leads to lack of conservation despite changes in appearance. The development of the child's ability to decenter is a marker of his progressing to the next stage of concrete operations. The concrete operations stage begins with progressive decentering in different tasks during the period lasting from about seven to about eleven years of age. By six or seven, most children are able to conserve number, length, and liquid volume. By nine or ten years of age, conservation of area is also mastered. In addition, the child can compare two or more things and therefore can classify them, or put them in order of magnitude during this stage.

The other constructivist theorist, Bruner (1964) proposed three modes of representation: enactive representation (action-based), iconic representation (image-based), and symbolic representation (language-based). Modes of representation are the different ways in which information is encoded and maintained in memory. A person actually uses all the modes of representation and they can also "translate" into each other, or may be combined in a single representation. Rather than being associated with neat age-related stages (like Piaget, 1951) the modes of representation as espoused by Bruner are only loosely sequential. Nevertheless, infants probably rely on enactive mode of representation. Children who are 1-6 years old primarily use the iconic mode of representation. Information is stored visually in the form of images (a mental picture). Very often, we remember childhood images even as adults. Indeed, our earliest memories are often images. As adults, some people are conscious of iconic representations and may actually use them, while others say they don't experience them. The dominant use of the iconic mode during early childhood explains why, when children are learning a new principle, it is often helpful to have diagrams or illustrations to accompany the verbal information. Nevertheless, from 7 years onwards, the symbolic mode dominates. In this mode, information is acquired in the form of a code or symbol, such as language. Knowledge is stored primarily as words, mathematical symbols, or in other symbol systems. This is the most adaptable form of representation. Symbols are flexible as they can be manipulated, combined, classified, ordered, etc. The user of symbolic mode of representation is no longer constrained by actions or images. As mentioned earlier, although Bruner adheres to the idea of stages in cognitive development, he doesn't see them exclusively associated with separate modes of representation at different points. Instead, he proposes a gradual development of cognitive skills and techniques into more integrated use of the three modes of representation in adulthood (Bruner, 1966).

In conclusion, it may be said that future researchers would need a precise assessment of the stage of cognitive development of a child (and the modes of representation that the child is using) and then investigate how the stage of development affects memory for bindings and single features. Not only would this yield an understanding of binding in the broader context of developmental literature, but it is likely that such studies would also aid the design of intervention programs for those who have difficulties with feature binding.

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